
ПРОБЛЕМИ, НАДБАННЯ І ПЕРСПЕКТИВИ ВІТЧИЗНЯНОЇ ТА ЗАРУБІЖНОЇ ПРОФЕСІЙНОЇ ОСВІТИ

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AXIOLOGICAL DEFINITENESS OF THE PROBLEM OF FORMING THE STUDENT'S HEALTH IN THE TERMS OF MODERN UNIVERSITY EDUCATION

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У статті здійснено емпіричне дослідження аксіологічної визначеності проблеми формування здорового способу життя студентської молоді в умовах сучасної університетської освіти. З'ясовано складний характер ієрархії цінностей сучасних студентів, особливостей формування їх ціннісних орієнтацій. Обґрунтовано, що в емпірично побудованій шкалі чинників, які зумовлюють вибір респондентами раціональних способів поведінки, перші рангові місця займають «бажання відчувати повноту і радість життя», «самореалізація у професії», «досягнення матеріального благополуччя». Застосовано методику визначення провідних цінностей студентів та сформульовано рекомендації для викладачів стосовно реалізації пропонованих аксіологічних чинників проблеми здоров'язбереження в умовах університету. Виявлено ступінь розуміння (усвідомлення) студентами значущості формування, збереження і зміцнення здоров'я для досягнення успіхів у навчанні (інтелектуальній сфері), самореалізації у майбутній професії.

Ключові слова: аксіологічна визначеність, здоров'я, здоровий спосіб життя, студентська молодь.

Introduction. While study the problem of axiological definiteness of forming the healthy way of youth's living we consider to focus the research interest on solving the following problems:

1. To characterize the innovations and to identify a specificity of psycho-educational approaches, which are characteristic for the process of practical solving of the problem of forming the youth's health in the terms of modern university education.

2. To determine the perspective trends of psycho-educational search in the theory and practice of forming the youth's health.

Results. Psycho-educational literature analyses let us come to the conclusion that the investigation of axiological definiteness of the problem of forming students' health was not separated as independent for a long time [1; 6]. Much attention was devoted to the study of the significance of pernicious habits prevention, physical culture trainings, controlled day regimen rationing, balanced nourishment of students for the purpose of improvement of their state of health.

The practice of the research results' dissemination by community health activity of health care authorities, entitative during several decades, did not have any appreciable positive

outcomes: students' acquirement of health knowledge does not guarantee that they will permanently concern themselves with it, keep the standards of healthy way of living in everyday life activities. Revealed general tendencies are corroborated by the data of our own observations and experimental studies. The research was carried out during the years from 2010 till 2016 and involved the students of Grinchenko Kyiv State Pedagogical University (now called Borys Grinchenko Kyiv University) (the number of involved students is 112), National Pedagogical Dragomanov University (the number of involved students is 106). The basic characteristics of students under consideration are: age – from 17 to 21 years, gender – male (67 persons), female (151 persons). The common characteristics of respondents are: belonging to the same age group – senior teen-age or student age; year of study – the first one; form of studies – full-time students.

While doing the research we seek to find out: if students of modern pedagogic university want to be healthy, if the values of healthy life-style are attractive for them, if they require receiving scientifically based knowledge in the field of health improvement, conservation and building up of their health? We consider that the answers to the questions under study were rooted in cognition of complex nature of modern students' values hierarchy, peculiarities of their values preferences forming, analyses of their specific requirements, interests, exhortations to preserve their health, adhere to healthy life-style.

Method. The method used for study the hierarchy of students' values was interviewing with using a questionnaire «My Life Values» [5, 413], which the respondents (112 persons) were ordered to fill in. The questionnaire represents the M. Rokich methodology based on the ranking of a number of values by the respondents and modified by the author. A calculation after Spierman's rank correlation coefficient was used as a ground for the analysis an occurrence and a level of an appearance of correlation between the «Bodily values» issue data and other values of future teachers. The choice of the statistical criterion was based on the data type (ordinal numeral) and the sample type (independent).

Discussion. The questionnaire consisted of the following basic sections: objective information (educational institution, department, year of study, group, date of filling in); respondents data (age, gender, marital status, living conditions, material security); the list of values (28 values) grouped in issues (6 issues): material, cultural, intelligent, moral, social, bodily. To make the data processing, grouping, analysis, tabulated demonstrations more comfortable each value has been labeled by a code:

I issue (material values): an accommodation – 1.1; a car – 1.2; clothes, footwear – 1.3; money – 1.4; a holiday home – 1.5;

II issue (cultural values): art (attendance of vernisages, exhibitions etc.) – 2.1; educational travelling – 2.2; fiction – 2.3; film art – 2.4; music (knowledge of popular art, folklore, world classic) – 2.5;

III issue (intelligent values): general erudition – 3.2; high professional status – 3.2; permanent work on rising the professional level (self-extension) – 3.3; self-expression in art, science etc. – 3.4;

IV issue (moral values): love of people, beneficence – 4.1; disinterestedness in treaties with family, friends – 4.2; kindness and humanity to living beings, nature – 4.3; sincerity, openness in communication – 4.4;

V issue (social values): social fulfillment, need to be useful for people and society and to receive a pleasure from it – 5.1; work as a source of social wellbeing – 5.2; serving the national interests, desire for native land protection – 5.3; patriotism – 5.4; assertion the priority of national heritage in education, upbringing – 5.5;

VI issue (bodily values): strong health – 6.1; sports achievements – 6.2; person's attractive appearance – 6.3; long living – 6.4; physical perfection (indulge in sports groups, gymnastics, running, jogging etc.) – 6.5.

The respondents were proposed to put values according to the order of the personal significance for them: beginning with the most valuable (the highest rank) – minimum (min) grade (1, 2, 3 ...), to the least valuable (the lowest rank) – maximum (max) grade (... 26, 27, 28). As the primary data have a quality character so relative values (%) has been chosen as an instrument for their statistic analyses. The data processing has been accomplished with the help of an average value computation method or an arithmetical mean. To get it the total sum of grades in each issue has been divided to the number of the data. The calculated coefficient is an indicator of a central tendency which made it possible to define a rank position of the values proposed in questionnaire according to their significance for the respondents.

To study, analyze and estimate the students' value orientations we used a consolidation of generalizing and individualizing research methods. A value ranking has been made on the base of mean values (M) which were considered to be a quantity (numerical) equivalent of a value measure of significance for an appointed sample body. The correlation of respondents' values hierarchy affords us an opportunity to establish a number of typical regularities. We should mention a fact that for a modern student his/her health as a value occupies the highest rank positions – the first, the second or the third one. The received data form the basis for thoughts as for axiological «Me» of a modern student. Thus for our research it has been significant to identify in a general values hierarchy the position of those that apply to health formation, preservation and building up. It was these view that assigned a logic of received data further analyses, description, interpreting.

The received data make it possible to establish which values are among the five most valuable ones for the respondents. As a huge quantity data array has been obtained it is appropriate to formulate the research results which are the most typical for the respondent body. Thereby students of Borys Grinchenko Kyiv University note that among the most significant values for them are moral (sincerity, openness in communication), intelligent (general erudition, professional self-extension), material (money, accommodation), bodily (strong health, attractive appearance). Students of National Pedagogical Dragomanov University speech are attracted by bodily (strong health), material (accommodation, money), moral (love of children, openness in communication with schoolchildren and colleges), intelligent (professional self-extension) values. The received data are represented on Figure 1.

Summarizing the received data it should be observed that the respondent university students consider to be the most significant bodily, material, intelligent, moral values and the least significant appeared cultural, social values, and among the bodily issue values the least significant proved to be sports, physical perfection. The drawn conclusion has been acknowledged by the results of the author's research aimed at an actual meaning of students' life activity exposure, particularly at leisure time, according to V. I. Bobrytska [2; 3; 4; 5]. Quite noticeable is also a fact that among different variants of students' attitude to the values of a healthy lifestyle most of the students express a positive attitude which is quite frequently combined with a conscious shortage of a proper knowledge, skills, acquired habits of their life activity organization based on a healthy lifestyle. While making oral comments to their attitude, the students accentuate that a desire to be healthy is equal to a desire to be professionally prosperous and happy in a family life.

Some students (approximately one third of them) express an opinion that a desire to preserve and build up their health during a university study can be met to a considerable degree by their owns exertions and can be implement on the assumption of an availability of high level theoretical training, a grasp of a broad spectrum of healthy life activity organization skills, a substantial awareness in up-to-date health preserving techniques. Such an attitude is typical for those respondents who put a factor «a desire to receive knowledge, skills, acquired habits of preserving their own health and health of the people around them, make use of health preserving techniques in a future professional activity» on a high rank. But a lack of a motivated position of

most of the students of the first year of study in their own life activity rationalization puts an averaged reckoning of the factor into the rank positions from the 5th to the 8th.

Figure 1. Rank distribution of university students' values

Another notable fact should also be noted. The submitted data reflect general tendencies while in individual responses an interesting regularities succession can be found. Thus a high level of «professional self-fulfillment» focus may be accompanied with a low level of «a desire to receive knowledge, skills, acquired habits of preserving their own health and health of the people around them, make use of health preserving techniques in a future professional activity». It suggests that some students are focused more on getting a university-level education but not on mastering some particular profession.

While analyzing the received data it has been revealed that students of all ages have almost identical content in motivational sphere. Thus the obtained data affirm that in empirically built scale of focuses which define a respondents' choice of rational way of behavior, the highest ranks are occupied by «a desire to meet the fullness and the joy of life», «professional self-fulfillment», «material wellbeing achievement because it's impossible to be achieved while having a poor health», as well as a focus indicative of students' comprehension of material advantages of preventive health care as compared with expenses on medical treatment – «it's much better to take care of your health in advance not to fall ill and spend up (it's much cheaper to prevent illness than to treat it)».

An emotional influence of certain healthy way of life option focuses which are connected to the professionally important empathy senses and care of others are insignificant. Thus the «responsibility for relatives and friends as a health status of each member of the family defines wellbeing and a peace of mind of other people» occupies the positions from the 9th to the 11th ranks in the general focuses hierarchy. Total impact of the listed focuses forms a core of the motivational sphere of the students of the first year of study which is implemented in their attitude to their health as a value, in a desire to correct the manners which are got into the habit (or in the absence of the desire), in urging to receive scientifically substantiate knowledge in the specified points, in self-education and in skills and acquired habits of healthy life activity organization perfection.

A significant moment in the experimental study milestone was a detection of a students' awareness level of a health essential characteristic, its axiological values and syncretic nature. Thus a significant interest for us had the seeking an answer to a question: If the students link the values of the bodily issue («strong health», «sports achievements», «physical perfection», «attractive appearance», «long living») together? As we see it, the respondents'

acknowledgement of the link occurrence of these values is a criterion of their syncretic characteristic's understanding as well as of an essential substance of healthy life style as a value because «sports achievements», «physical perfection» are a method, «attractive appearance» is a measure, «long living» is a result of a strong health achievement.

As it is depicted by the data in Figure 1, the sample who attach a particular importance to «strong health» in the value rank, give the rest of the issue values («sports achievements», «physical perfection», «attractive appearance», «long living») mostly the twenties and thirties rank.

This fact proves the fact that the students have no clear consciousness of bodily values interdependence and interrelationship that to our mind is an evidence of the lack of their science-based knowledge of the problem under research. The received data give us a possibility to define a students' comprehension level (level of understanding) of the significance of forming, preserving, strengthening of their health for academic progress achievement (intelligent issue), self-fulfillment in a future profession.

Let us analyze an occurrence and a level of an appearance of correlation between the «Bodily values» issue data and other values of future teachers. A calculation after Spierman's rank correlation coefficient was used as a ground for the analysis. The choice of the statistical criterion was based on the data type (ordinal numeral) and the sample type (independent).

While data analyzes it turned out that only 19,64 % of respondents are conscious of the significance of keeping a healthy life style for obtaining a professional education (positive correlation) and 37,5 % of respondents do not link the bodily issue values to perspectives of getting a success in their studies (in future profession). 42,86 % of respondents represented a low correlation between the mentioned parameters. Besides the research revealed that for most of the students a strong health is a guarantee of a material wellbeing: existence of a positive correlation between the issues «Material values» and «Bodily values» factors accounts for 85,71 %, in 34,82 % of which correlation is close (strong one). Only 14,29 % of future teachers consider a strong health not to be an essential condition for receiving a material wellbeing. As for the issues «Bodily values» and «Social values» data factors, it was established that 63,39 % of respondents discover a positive correlation; 28,57 % have no correlation at all or it is too small; 8,04 % have a negative correlation.

The obtained data interpreting as for the existence of correlation link between the dimensions «bodily issue values» and «values-motives» made it possible to expose the students' readiness to forming their health during the period of study in university. Besides the survey results made it possible to come into conclusion that a professional orientation is one of the determinants of that activity activization which brings the students nearer to understanding an inner unity of professional treatment process and their life style and is a regulator of the students' conscious choice of efficient (healthy) mode of everyday life activity organization. In addition, a desire to be healthy which is inherent to the most of the respondents involved in the research, slightly brings them closely to comprehension of the fact that an active healthy life style bearer is a concrete person (each of them) as an object and a subject of his/her life style. That is why the essential content of the notion «health formation» is still hidden for the students of the first year of study. It is created the impression that for the tested age range health is some kind of an ontological value which is given to everyone together with life by nature and that it exists entitative from the real efforts of a person as for its forming, conservation and strengthening.

Conclusions. The research of an axiological definition of the problem of forming the students' health in the terms of modern university education at an applied level gives us a possibility to find out that taking the health as a value is not considered to be an effective regulator of everyday behavior for the most of the university students and slightly influences long-term intentions to change acquired stereotypes. Most of the persons engaged in the research represented a positive attitude to the healthy life style as a factor of an «ideal» method of

forming their health. At the same time they noted that in a real life there are many independent and subjective circumstances that are interfere with the realization of the intention to improve their living conditions and their life styles, particularly their disorganization, business of learning tasks and everyday engagements, the lack of knowledge of the methods of health improvement etc.

Verification of the performed theoretical generalizations and the experimental study detected the necessity of the development of scientific and methodological foundations of health of the youth in university study.

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Бобрицкая В.И.

АКСИОЛОГИЧЕСКАЯ ДЕТЕРМИНИРОВАННОСТЬ ПРОБЛЕМЫ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ЗДОРОВЬЯ СТУДЕНТОВ В УСЛОВИЯХ СОВРЕМЕННОГО УНИВЕРСИТЕТСКОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ

В статье осуществлено эмпирическое исследование аксиологической детерминированности проблемы формирования здорового образа жизни студентов в условиях современного университетского образования. Определен сложный характер иерархии ценностей современных студентов, особенностей формирования их ценностных ориентаций. Обосновано, что в эмпирически построенной шкале факторов, которые определяют выбор респондентами рациональных способов поведения, первые ранговые места занимают «желание ощущать полноту и радость жизни», «самореализация в профессии», «достижение материального благополучия». Использована методика исследования определенных качеств студентов и сформулированы рекомендации для преподавателей относительно реализации предложенных аксиологических факторов решения проблемы сохранения здоровья студентов в условиях университета. Выявлена степень понимания студентами значимости формирования, сохранения и укрепления здоровья для достижения успехов в образовании (интеллектуальной сфере), самореализации в будущей профессии.

Ключевые слова: аксиологическая детерминированность, здоровье, здоровый образ жизни, студенческая молодежь.

BOBRYTSKA V. I.

AXIOLOGICAL DEFINITENESS OF THE PROBLEM OF FORMING THE STUDENT'S HEALTH IN THE TERMS OF MODERN UNIVERSITY EDUCATION

The article provides an insight into the empirical study to have been conducted on the problem of axiological definiteness to the formation of a healthy lifestyle of students in the settings of modern tertiary education. It reveals the complex nature of the hierarchy of values of modern students, specifics of formation of their value orientations.

The article discovers that physical, material, intellectual, moral values are of the greatest importance for students of the modern universities while cultural and social values are of the least significance and sport along with physical development are among the values of the physically-aimed group of values. It has been elucidated that the attitude towards the values of a healthy lifestyle gains approval by most students, and this attitude is combined with the awareness of the students' lack of knowledge, skills and abilities to organize their life on the basis of a healthy lifestyle principles.

The article provides proofs that on the empirically constructed scale of factors that determine the choice of respondents for rational behaviours, the «desire to feel fullness and joy of life», «opportunities of self-realization in the profession», «achievement of material well-being» occupy the leading rank positions.

The method used for study the hierarchy of students' values was interviewing with using a questionnaire «My Life Values» [5, 413], which the respondents (112 persons) were ordered to fill in. The questionnaire represents the M. Rokich methodology based on the ranking of a number of values by the respondents and modified by the author. A calculation after Spierman's rank correlation coefficient was used as a ground for the analysis an occurrence and a level of an appearance of correlation between the «Bodily values» issue data and other values of future teachers. The choice of the statistical criterion was based on the data type (ordinal numeral) and the sample type (independent.)

It reveals the degree of understanding (awareness of) the importance of forming, preserving and strengthening health by the students for achieving success in their studies (intellectual sphere), self-realization in their future career.

Verification of the performed theoretical generalizations and the experimental study detected the necessity of the development of scientific and methodological foundations of health of the youth in university study.

Key words: axiological definiteness, health, healthy lifestyle, student youth.

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